

Assessment of the circularity and renewability of materials through thermoeconomics and exergy. The case of metals from Printed Circuit Boards.

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ABSTRACT

The circular economy driven by renewable energies is one of the keys to the sustainability of industrialized societies. However, the quantification of both circularity and renewability of materials is not trivial as it combines both material terms, usually measured in mass, and energy terms, measured in energy units. In this sense, the use of exergy is proved as a solution, since materials can be evaluated through exergy cost and renewable energy through exergy. Thus it is possible to assess both the circularity and renewability of materials using the single criterion of exergy. This study uses the case study of metals embedded in a printed circuit board (PCB) to illustrate these ideas. It considers the extraction of metals, and the production and recycling of the PCB. The disaggregation of the exergy cost allows to identify the destruction of exergy (irreversibilities) and the origin of the exergy either non-renewable and renewable. Thus, the results show that the circularity of the PCB circular economy is between 27.3 and 49.6 % depending on the deployment of renewable technologies. In other words, in a circular economy cycle between three quarters and half of the resources measured in exergy are destroyed. On the other hand, renewability, i.e. the percentage of renewable irreversibilities lost in relation to the total is between 12.9 and 79.4%, depending on the deployment of renewables. The use of renewable technologies improves both indicators significantly. However, better strategies are needed to increase these indicators to ensure the sustainability of production processes in the long term.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the industrial revolution, the consumption of non-renewable resources has steadily increased in both quantity and diversity. For example, the extraction of fossil fuels has risen from 6,000 TWh in 1900 to 140,000 TWh in 2020, reflecting an exponential growth rate of 2.7% per year Institute, 2024. The extraction of minerals shows an even greater increase. In 1900, it was barely 60 million tons, while in 2020 it reached 3 billion tons, with an exponential growth rate of 5.3% annually Center, 2024. In response to this situation, both the circular economy and renewable energy sources are presented as solutions. On one hand, the circular economy aims to transform waste into resources through various strategies ranging from reuse to recycling. On the other hand, renewable technologies can capture renewable energy from nature to be used in productive processes. However, neither the circular economy nor renewable energy technologies can guarantee the recovery of all waste. This is because recycling always requires new resources, and it is impossible to recover 100% of the mass. Additionally, renewable technologies depend on non-renewable resources such as minerals and metals, and they use oil, natural gas, or coal in their extraction and refining processes. Given this situation, one might ask: How circular and renewable is the circular economy?

To answer this question, it is necessary to use the appropriate tools. In this regard, exergy is the best thermodynamic property to assess the renewability and circularity of the circular economy for several reasons. First, it indicates the useful work required to carry out any economic-production process, i.e., to transform nature into goods. Second, exergy is not conserved, which means it measures the quantity and quality of resources lost in each transformation process, a phenomenon known as irreversibility. This is the fundamental difference with energy, which is conserved and, therefore, cannot measure the quality of resources. Third, exergy allows the unification of energy and matter through exergy cost, which represents all the exergy needed to produce a product Valero et al., 1986.

Other authors have previously studied the limitations of recycling, the circular economy, and renewables Aramendia et al., 2024; Capellán-Pérez et al., 2019; Diesendorf and Wiedmann, 2020; Reuter et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019. However, to the author's knowledge, no work has performed an exergy analysis of a full cycle considering both circularity and renewability. This study uses the case of metals from a printed circuit board, as these devices are essential in any electronic product, and their production continues to grow due to the ongoing digital transition.

2 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The evaluation of the circularity and renewability of materials requires knowledge of the exergy costs at different stages of the circular economy. This study uses a case of 20 tons of PCBs, whose chemical composition and, therefore, demand for metals and materials, is based on previous works Torrubia, Parvez, et al., 2024; Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2024 (see Table 3).

Section 2.1 presents the methodology used to calculate the exergy cost of primary extraction of metals and materials, while section 2.2 describes the exergy cost of PCB recycling. Section 2.3 explains the methodology for the exergy evaluation of the circular economy, outlining the role of intermediate stages between extraction and recycling.

2.1 Exergy cost of primary extraction

Primary extraction is the first stage. In this stage, all the necessary resources are extracted, which will later be recycled. The case study in this article focuses on the metals from a PCB. The metals that contribute most to the exergy cost of the studied PCB are copper, silver, gold, and palladium. Therefore, the first step is to determine the energy resources required to extract these metals. This data is obtained from previous work Torrubia et al., 2023, which provides detailed information on the electricity and fossil fuels required. This disaggregation is crucial for understanding the origin (non-renewable or renewable) of the exergy.

Table 1: Exergy cost of primary extraction of metals. Data obtained from Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024.

MJ/kg	Coal	Oil	NG	Electricity
Cu	3.48	0.70	0.68	18.28
Ag	3043	424	416	7277
Au	11249	77329	75870	143794
Pd	21	60806	59659	61951

Once the energy inputs are known, they must be converted into exergy costs. To do this, the data obtained from previous works Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024 and Lima et al., 2025 are used, as shown in Table 2. The work Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024 presents the exergy cost of fossil fuels and electricity for 2020 and 2050, while Lima et al., 2025 provides the exergy cost of hydrogen for 2050 only. This table displays the exergy cost breakdown for each energy resource used in the extraction of the metals. It is broken down into exergy and irreversibility, as well as renewable and non-renewable, which includes coal, oil, natural gas, and nuclear. Irreversibilities are only present in electricity and hydrogen, as they represent all the resources destroyed in their production.

This work uses two scenarios, as shown in Table 2:

- 2020 scenario: It uses conventional fossil fuels and the global electricity mix of 2020.
- 2050 scenario: It assumes a substitution of fossil fuels with renewable hydrogen and uses the 2020 electricity mix according to the IEA's NZE scenario International Energy Agency, 2021. As seen in Table 2, although nearly all exergy in this scenario comes from renewable sources, the irreversibilities are not renewable, as non-renewable resources are always required for infrastructure production.

Finally, this work also considers the chemical exergy of the minerals used in the primary extraction of metals. The exergy of these minerals is destroyed during metal production. In some cases, this can be significant, as in the case of copper. Its ore is chalcopyrite, which has an exergy of 8.34 MJ/kg due to its high sulfur content. The chemical exergy has been considered based on the reference by Szargut Szargut et al., 1988.

Thus, starting from the energy consumption divided into fossil fuels and electricity, we multiply each fuel by its exergy cost (Table 2) and then add the chemical exergy. This procedure results in the term $B_{Extraction}^*$ for copper, silver, gold, and palladium, broken down into: renewable and non-renewable, further subdivided into the chemical exergy of the minerals, fossil fuels, nuclear, and the non-renewable exergy cost of renewable infrastructure.

2.2 Exergy cost of recycling

One of the key stages in the circular economy is recycling. In this stage, materials that have lost their utility value are recovered. However, this recovery process also requires new resources, primarily fossil fuels, electricity, and chemicals.

Table 2: Exergy cost of fuels disaggregated in exergy-irreversibility and non-renewable-renewable. Data obtained from Torrubiá, Valero, and Valero, 2024 and Lima et al., 2025.

Exergy Cost	Coal	Oil	Natural Gas	Electricity 2020	Electricity 2050	H ₂ 2050
Renewable Exergy				0.28	0.91	1
Coal Exergy	1.06			0.35	0	
Oil Exergy		1.06		0.03	0	
Natural Gas Exergy			1.04	0.23	0	
Nuclear Exergy				0.1	0.08	
Renewable Irreversibility				0	0.01	0.46
Coal Irreversibility				0.71	0.02	0.16
Oil Irreversibility				0.08	0.01	0.06
Natural Gas Irreversibility				0.28	0.02	0.09
Nuclear Irreversibility				0	0	0.01

As mentioned previously, this work recycles 20 tons of PCB, the chemical composition of which is detailed in Table 3. The recycling process used is based on a metallurgical simulation, which is the result of prior work.

Table 3: PCB composition. Data obtained from Torrubiá, Parvez, et al., 2024.

Waste PCB (wt%)												
Total Metallic	Cu	Fe	Al	Sn	Pb	Ni	Zn	Ag	Au	Pd	Ta	Co
40%	22	6	4	3	3	1	0.8	0.1	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02
Total Plastic	C ₃ H ₆	C ₂ F ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₂ H ₃ Cl	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₄					
30%	5	2	10	2	5	5	1					
Total Ceramic	SiO ₂	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	TiO ₂					
30%	15	2	6	1	1	2	3					

Thus, this recycling process manages to recover approximately 95% of the copper and 99% of the silver, gold, and palladium. It is also important to note that all plastics (30% of the PCB mass) are consumed in the process, as they are used as fuel, transforming into CO₂. On the other hand, the article Torrubiá, Parvez, et al., 2024 proposes two scenarios: 1) conventional energies, which use coke and natural gas, and 2) renewable energies, which replace coke and natural gas with hydrogen. These two scenarios align with the ones proposed in section 2.2. In this way, the 2020 scenario uses conventional energies with the 2020 electricity mix, while the 2050 scenario employs hydrogen with the 2050 electricity mix. Table 4 shows the inputs required to recycle one kg of PCB.

Table 4: Exergy cost of recycling one kg of PCB. Data obtained from Torrubiá, Parvez, et al., 2024.

MJ/ kg	Coal	Oil	NG	Electricity
PCB	1.91	0.29	1.22	1.08

However, apart from knowing the necessary inputs, there are other important parameters in the recycling process. These are: $B_{R-Resources}^*$, I_{R-ML} , and I_{R-W} . $B_{R-Resources}^*$ represents all the resources needed to carry out the recycling process. This term includes not only the direct inputs from Table 4, but also the indirect ones, meaning the exergy of the plastics used in the recycling process. The recycling process also involves irreversibilities due to mass loss, as not all material is recovered, and the generation of waste. These two parameters are denoted as I_{R-ML} and I_{R-W} , respectively. The values of these parameters are obtained from previous work Torrubiá, Torres, et al., 2024, which conducts a thermoeconomic analysis of the recycling process. The analysis proposes several allocation methods based on exergy. However, in this work, only the exergy-based allocation method is used, as analyzing different allocation methods is outside the scope of this study. Once all the necessary inputs for recycling are known, the exergy cost is calculated by multiplying by the exergy costs from Table 2. Thus, both primary extraction and recycling follow the same calculation logic.

Finally, the goal of recycling is to save resources. Thus, B_{Saved}^* represents the exergy cost saved or avoided from primary extraction due to recycling. In other words, it represents the exergy cost produced during metal extraction, $B_{Extraction}^*$, which is recovered during the recycling process and reintroduced into a new economic cycle. In this way, these four terms are obtained, broken down in the same way as primary extraction: renewable and non-renewable, further subdivided into: chemical exergy of the plastics, fossil fuels, nuclear, and the non-renewable exergy cost of renewable infrastructure.

2.3 Exergy evaluation of circular economy

Extraction and recycling represent the first and last stages of the circular economy. However, there are numerous intermediate stages depending on the depth of the analysis, such as production (or manufacturing), transportation (or distribution), reuse, repair, or collection. This article considers only two: production and collection. However, the collection stage is only discussed briefly due to the lack of data, as a 100% collection rate is assumed.

Production is the stage where raw materials, extracted in section 2.2, are used to manufacture the product, in this case, a PCB. In this way, we estimate the electrical consumption required to assemble the metals and materials as 87.5 kWh/kg of PCB, based on the data from [Yu et al., 2010]. This electrical consumption can be converted into exergy cost using the results from the article Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024, discussed in previous sections. This exergy cost is referred to as $B_{Production}^*$. Thus, the exergy cost of a product ($B_{Product}^*$), in this case, 20 tons of PCB, will be the sum of the exergy cost of extracting its materials ($B_{Extraction}^*$) and the exergy cost of production ($B_{Production}^*$), as indicated by equation 1.

$$B_{Product}^* = B_{Extraction}^* + B_{Production}^* \quad (1)$$

Products eventually reach the end of their useful life. When this happens, they lose their use value, and therefore, their value is reduced to the materials that make up the product. In this way, end-of-life irreversibilities (I_{EoL}) are generated, which include all the exergy cost produced between the extraction of the materials ($B_{Extraction}^*$) and the exergy cost of the product ($B_{Product}^*$), that is, $B_{Production}^*$ in this case, as indicated by equation 2.

$$I_{EoL} = B_{Production}^* \quad (2)$$

Once I_{EoL} is defined, B_{EoL}^* can be calculated using equation 3. B_{EoL}^* represents the exergy cost of the materials in the product when it reaches the end of its useful life. From equations 1 and 2, it can be deduced that in this case, B_{EoL}^* is equal to $B_{Extraction}^*$. This is because the exergy cost of transportation, which should be added to B_{EoL}^* , is not considered in the calculation presented in this work.

$$B_{EoL}^* = B_{Product}^* - I_{EoL} \quad (3)$$

Not all end-of-life products reach the recycling plant. They must first be collected and transported to the plant. However, collection incurs exergy costs ($B_{Collection}^*$), and only a certain percentage of the total is collected ($\%Collection$). Due to these two factors, collection irreversibilities ($I_{Collection}$) are generated, which can be calculated using equation 4. The parameters $B_{Collection}^*$ and $\%Collection$ depend on the geographical location of the waste. Therefore, in this work, the most optimistic scenario is considered, meaning that $B_{Collection}^*$ is 0 MJ and $\%Collection$ is 100%. Thus, $I_{Collection}$ is equal to 0 MJ. As a result, the irreversibilities generated up to collection ($I_{Collected}$) are the same as those of I_{EoL} (see equation 5), since no new irreversibilities are generated during collection. Similarly, the exergy cost of the collected materials ($B_{Collected}^*$), which can potentially be saved during recycling, is equal to B_{EoL}^* , because it is assumed that 100% of the end-of-life products are collected (see equation 6).

$$I_{Collection} = B_{EoL}^* \cdot (1 - \%Collection) + B_{Collection}^* \quad (4)$$

$$I_{Collected} = I_{EoL} + I_{Collection} \quad (5)$$

$$B_{Collected}^* = B_{EoL}^* + \%Collection \quad (6)$$

Once the products have been collected, they reach the recycling plant. This process is explained in section 2.2. From the recycling process, the terms $B_{R-Recycling}^*$ are obtained, which represent the exergy costs of the resources used in recycling, I_{R-ML} and I_{R-W} , which represent the irreversibilities of the recycling process. I_{R-ML} is due to mass losses, while I_{R-W} is due to the waste generated in the process. Thus, the sum of these three parameters represents the exergy costs of recycling, $B_{Recycling}^*$, as shown in equation 7.

$$B_{Recycling}^* = B_{R-Resources}^* + I_{R-ML} + I_{R-W} \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, B_{Saved}^* represents the exergy cost saved or avoided from primary extraction due to recycling, as explained in section 2.2. Once the parameters B_{Saved}^* , $B_{Collected}^*$, $B_{Recycling}^*$, and $I_{Collected}$ are known, the exergy efficiency of recycling ($\epsilon_{Recycling}$) and of the circular economy (ϵ_{CE}) can be calculated through equations 8 and 9.

$$\epsilon_{Recycling} = \frac{B_{Saved}^*}{B_{Collected}^* + B_{Recycling}^*} = \frac{B_{Saved}^*}{B_{To-Recycle}^*} \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon_{CE} = \frac{B_{Saved}^*}{B_{Collected}^* + B_{Recycling}^* + I_{Collected}} = \frac{B_{Saved}^*}{B_{CE}^*} \quad (9)$$

$\epsilon_{Recycling}$ and ϵ_{CE} differ in that ϵ_{CE} considers the irreversibilities up to collection ($I_{Collected}$) as losses. It is important to remember here that $I_{Collected}$ is equal to I_{EoL} in this case because $I_{Collection}$ is considered 0 MJ. Thus, $\epsilon_{Recycling}$ only takes into account the maximum exergy cost that can be recovered from what enters recycling (i.e., $B_{To-Recycle}^*$), while ϵ_{CE} considers the exergy cost of the entire circular economy (B_{CE}^*), including the irreversibilities lost in processes prior to recycling, i.e., $I_{Collected}$.

All the exergy costs mentioned above are disaggregated into non-renewable and renewable, as explained in sections 2.1 and 2.2. This way, it is possible not only to identify where irreversibilities are generated, lost, or saved, but also to determine whether they are non-renewable or renewable. This is important because, although the generation of irreversibilities is inevitable according to the second law of thermodynamics, if they are renewable, the sustainability of the processes can be ensured. Therefore, it is crucial to know what percentage of all the lost irreversibilities is renewable. To do this, it is necessary first to calculate all the accumulated lost irreversibilities ($I_{Collected}$), which will be the difference between the total exergy cost of the circular economy (B_{CE}^*) and the exergy cost saved (B_{Saved}^*), as indicated in equation 10. Furthermore, by knowing the disaggregation between non-renewable and renewable, it is possible to determine the accumulated renewable lost irreversibilities ($I_{Accumulated-REN}$), which represent the renewable fraction of ($I_{Accumulated}$). With these terms, it is possible to calculate the renewable exergy efficiency $\epsilon_{Renewable}$, using equation 11.

$$I_{Accumulated} = B_{CE}^* - B_{Saved}^* \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{Renewable} = \frac{I_{Accumulated-REN}}{I_{Accumulated}} \quad (11)$$

In summary, this methodology allows for the establishment of three key indicators of the circular economy: $\epsilon_{Recycling}$, which indicates the exergy efficiency of recycling alone; ϵ_{CE} , which indicates the exergy efficiency of the entire circular economy, i.e., its circularity; and $\epsilon_{Renewable}$, which represents the percentage of lost renewable irreversibilities, i.e., it indicates the renewability of the circular economy.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 3.1 compares the exergy cost of the primary extraction of the main metals from a PCB (Cu, Ag, Au, Pd), explained in Section 2.1, with the exergy cost of their recycling, explained in Section 2.2. On the other hand, Section 3.2 broadens the scope and analyzes the circularity and renewability of the PCB's circular economy.

3.1 Primary extraction vs Recycling

Figure 1 shows the exergy cost results for the metals Cu, Ag, Au, and Pd, both from primary extraction and recycling from PCBs. The exergy cost is broken down into non-renewable, which includes the following categories: 1) non-renewable infrastructure, 2) nuclear, 3) fossil fuels, 4) chemical exergy (from minerals (primary extraction) or PCB plastics (recycling)), and 5) renewable. Two scenarios are distinguished: 2020 (using conventional technologies) and 2050 (using renewable technologies). Additionally, two allocation systems are defined for recycling: B^* or ERC , depending on the current or future consideration.

First, the primary extraction scenarios are analyzed. Figure 1 shows that gold has the highest exergy cost in all scenarios, followed by palladium, silver, and copper. Regarding the origin of this exergy cost, in the 2020 scenario, non-renewable exergy stands out in all cases, accounting for 92%, 90%, 92%, and 91% for Cu, Ag, Au, and Pd,

Primary Exergy Cost of Metals (Primary Extraction vs Recycling Resources)

Figure 1: Exergy cost results comparing primary extraction and recycling of metals.

respectively. On the other hand, in the 2050 scenario, the non-renewable contribution decreases to 48%, 24%, 19%, and 17%, respectively. Copper has the highest non-renewable percentage due to the chemical exergy of chalcocopyrite, which does not decrease despite the introduction of renewable technologies. The decrease in the non-renewable contribution occurs even though the total exergy cost remains in the same order of magnitude for both the 2020 and 2050 scenarios (65 vs 53 MJ/kg for copper; 21.381 vs 18.508 MJ/kg for silver; 502.621 vs 799.231 MJ/kg for gold; and 201.388 vs 211.507 MJ/kg for palladium).

Second, the recycling scenarios are analyzed. Figure 1 shows that the non-renewable contribution to the exergy cost of recycling is 90% in all cases in the 2020 scenario, with the contribution of chemical exergy from plastics (B Chem (plastics)) standing out at 65%. This is because plastics are used as fuel for the recycling process. This high contribution could only be avoided by separately collecting the plastics from the PCB before introducing them into the recycling process. For this reason, when renewable technologies are employed in the recycling process, the non-renewable contribution decreases to 85%.

Third, a comparison is made between primary extraction and recycling. All metals show significant savings when recycled. For example, in the 2020 scenario, the savings are 92.2% for copper, 93.3% for silver, 92.7% for gold, and 92.8% for palladium.

In addition to the global exergy savings, it is important to analyze the savings in non-renewable exergy, as saving this type of exergy should be a priority since the natural resources it represents are lost permanently when destroyed. Thus, the non-renewable disaggregation in Figure 1 allows for the construction of Table 5, which shows the non-renewable exergy costs.

Table 5 shows that starting from the worst scenario, primary extraction with conventional technologies, the non-renewable exergy cost could be reduced by between 56.7% (in the case of copper) and 80.9% (in the case of

Table 5: Non-renewable exergy cost (b_{NR}^*) of metals. E indicates primary extraction, R , indicates recycling, 2020 scenario and 2050 scenario.

	Cu		Ag		Au		Pd	
	b_{NR}^* (MJ/kg)	Saving (%)	b_{NR}^* (MJ/kg)	Saving (%)	b_{NR}^* (MJ/kg)	Saving (%)	b_{NR}^* (MJ/kg)	Saving (%)
b_{E-2020}^*	60	-	19,302	-	461,548	-	183,693	-
b_{E-2050}^*	26	56.7%	4,403	77.2%	153,171	66.8%	35,053	80.9%
b_{R-2020}^*	5	91.7%	1,406	92.7%	35,721	92.3%	14,232	92.3%
b_{R-2050}^*	3	95.0%	1,271	93.4%	32,792	92.9%	9,067	95.1%

palladium). The exergy cost savings for copper are lower (only 56.7%) because the chemical exergy in chalcopyrite (which is non-renewable) cannot be saved by introducing renewable technologies. Using conventional technologies for recycling, the savings would increase to between 91.7% and 92.7%, and could reach 93.4% and 95.1% with the renewable technologies in the 2050 scenario. The improvement with the use of renewable technologies in recycling is not very large (only increasing by 0.7 to 3.3 percentage points) because much of the non-renewable exergy cost of recycling is due to the plastics embedded in the PCB. This exergy cost could only be avoided if the plastics were separated from the PCB beforehand.

The comparison of the exergy cost of extraction and recycling clearly shows the advantages of recycling in terms of exergy savings. However, this is not enough to fully understand the scope of the circular economy. This will be addressed in the next section.

3.2 How circular is circular economy?

Figures 2 and 3 represent the full circular economy cycle of a PCB, considering the origin of natural resources for the 2020 scenario. Figure 2 shows the circular economy cycle, while Figure 3 illustrates all the processes required to supply the resources, including fossil fuels, electricity, and chemicals. The exergy cost of each flow is broken down into: exergy (blue tones) and irreversibility (red tones), as well as renewable (light tones) and non-renewable (dark tones). This way, it is possible to identify at which stages irreversibilities occur and how more renewable exergy can be captured.

The system inputs are always in the form of exergy (renewable exergy, 2284 GJ; nuclear fuel, 816 GJ; fossil fuel deposits, 14797+736 GJ (in Figure 3); and mineral deposits, 418 GJ (in Figure 2)), except for the exergy cost of the infrastructure (310 GJ, in Figure 3), as this exergy cost was transformed into irreversibility in the past due to the manufacturing process. Thus, Figure 3 shows how all the exergy of natural resources is transformed into irreversibility when using resources such as electricity, fossil fuels, or chemicals. It highlights the 266 GJ of renewable infrastructure required to capture 2284 GJ of renewable exergy, or the 8671 GJ of irreversibilities produced to generate 8056 GJ of electricity.

Figure 2: Sankey diagram of circular economy of metals from PCB. 2020 Scenario. All flows are measure in GJ.

Supply processes CE of PCB - 2020 Scenario (GJ)

Figure 3: Sankey diagram of the supply processes for the circular economy of metals from PCB. 2020 Scenario. All flows are measure in GJ.

Once all the supply resources are obtained, the circular economy of a PCB is analyzed (Figure 2). It starts with the extraction of the necessary natural resources to manufacture a PCB. In this stage, 5698 MJ of fuels, electricity, and chemicals, along with 418 GJ of minerals, are used to produce Cu, Ag, Pd, Au, and other materials needed for the PCB. It can be observed that the metals account for most of the exergy cost, 5540 GJ, compared to 576 GJ for other materials. The other materials have 289 GJ of exergy, mainly due to plastics.

After extracting the materials, they are assembled in the microchip factory, where 6303 GJ of exergy (plus 6784 GJ of irreversibility) is used. This stage consumes the most exergy, more than the extraction stage (3668 GJ, plus 2030 GJ of irreversibility). This is one of the reasons for the low performance of the circular economy in this example, as in the end-of-life stage, all this exergy cost is lost in the form of irreversibility (13086 GJ).

The next process is recycling, as collection has not been considered in this example. In this stage, 289 GJ of exergy (plastics) and 5827 GJ of irreversibility are input, from which 5464 GJ can be recovered to be recirculated. However, 160 GJ must be invested to carry out this recovery.

The Sankey diagrams in Figures 2 and 3 show in detail the origin of the exergy, its transformation into irreversibility, and the processes in which it is lost. Furthermore, they provide all the necessary information to calculate $\epsilon_{Recycling}$, ϵ_{CE} , and $\epsilon_{Renewable}$. In Figure 2, the following terms are highlighted: 1) PCB exergy cost, referring to $B^*_{Product}$; 2) PCB EoL exergy cost (B^*_{EoL}); 3) Irreversibility (EoL) (I_{EoL}); 4) Exergy cost invested in collection ($B^*_{Collection}$); 5) Irreversibility (collection) ($I_{Collection}$); 6) PCB collected exergy cost ($B^*_{Collected}$); 7) Exergy cost of recycling resources (B^*_{M-R}); 8) Saved exergy cost (B^*_{Saved}); 9) Irreversibility (mass losses) (I_{R-ML}); and 10) Irreversibility (waste) (I_{R-W}). These terms have been previously defined in Section 2.2, and their values are represented in Table 6. Thus, Table 6 shows all the necessary variables and the calculation of $\epsilon_{Recycling}$, ϵ_{CE} , and $\epsilon_{Renewable}$, i.e., the indicators of circularity and renewability of the circular economy. It shows the two scenarios, 2020 and 2050.

First, the results of $\epsilon_{Recycling}$ and ϵ_{CE} are analyzed for both scenarios. The recycling exergy efficiency ($\epsilon_{Recycling}$)

Table 6: calculation of circularity and renewability indicators: **Exergy efficiency of recycling** ($\epsilon_{Recycling}$), the **Exergy efficiency of circular economy** (ϵ_{CE}), and **renewable exergy efficiency** ($\epsilon_{Renewable}$) of PCBs. Note that this paper consider 100% of collection which makes $B_{Collected}^*$ and $I_{Collected}$ equal to B_{EoL}^* and I_{EoL} , respectively

	Symbol	Description	Eq.	2020 scenario	2050 scenario
a)	$B_{Product}^*$	PCB Exergy Cost	[1]	19202	14990
b)	I_{EoL}	Irreversibility lost (EoL)	[2]	13086	6684
c)	B_{EoL}^*	PCB EoL Exergy cost	[3]	6116	8306
d)	$\%_{Collected}$	Percentaje collected		100%	100%
e)	$B_{Collection}^*$	Exergy Cost invested in collection		0	0
f)	$I_{Collection}$	Irreversibility lost (Collection) [$c \cdot (1 - d) + e$]	[4]	0	0
g)	$I_{Collected}$	Irreversibility of PCB EoL collected [$b + f$]	[5]	13086	6684
h)	$B_{Collected}^*$	Exergy cost of PCB EoL collected [$c \cdot d$]	[6]	6116	8306
i)	$B_{R-Recycling}^*$	Exergy Cost of Recycling Resources		427	422
j)	I_{R-ML}	Irreversibility lost (Recycling mass losses)		363	244
k)	I_{R-W}	Irreversibility lost (Recycling Waste)		21	20
l)	$B_{Recycling}^*$	Recycling exergy cost [$i + j + k$]	[7]	811	686
m)	B_{Saved}^*	Saved Exergy Cost		5464	7773
n)	$B_{To-Recycle}^*$	Exergy cost of recycling [$g + l$]	[8]	6927	8992
o)	$\epsilon_{Recycling}$	Exergy efficiency of recycling [m/n]	[8]	78.9%	86.4%
p)	b_{CE}^*	Exergy cost of circular economy [$g + h + l$]	[9]	20013	15676
q)	ϵ_{CE}	Exergy efficiency of circular economy [m/p]	[9]	27.30%	49.59%
r)	$I_{Accumulated}$	Irreversibility Accumulated [$p - m$]	[10]	14549	7903
s)	$I_{Accumulated-REN}$	Irreversibility Accumulated renewable [$p - m$]	[10]	1874	6274
t)	$\epsilon_{renewable}$	Renewable exergy efficiency [s/r]	[11]	12.9%	79.4%

is 78.9% in the 2020 scenario and increases to 86.4% in the 2050 scenario. This improvement in 2050 is due to a greater savings in exergy cost (B_{Saved}^* , 7773 GJ compared to 5464 GJ), as primary production in 2050 requires more exergy, as shown in Figure 1. These percentages are quite high and satisfactory, considering that all the resources invested in recycling are also accounted for. However, to have a complete view of the circular economy, it is necessary to analyze ϵ_{CE} , as it takes other process losses into account. As a result, it can be seen that ϵ_{CE} drops significantly in both scenarios. In the 2020 scenario, efficiency decreases to 27.3%, which is a 51.6 percentage point drop. Similarly, in the 2050 scenario, it falls to 49.6%, a decrease of 36.9 percentage points. This drop occurs because irreversibilities at the end of life (I_{EoL}) are considered. These irreversibilities happen because the product loses its usefulness, making them irrecoverable in the recycling process. The 2020 scenario shows a more pronounced drop because $I_{Collected}$ is 13,086 GJ, while in 2050, it is 6684 GJ. This difference is due to the fact that the electricity in the 2050 scenario has much fewer irreversibilities because it is based on renewable technologies. On the other hand, electrical irreversibilities in the 2020 scenario are very high (to produce 8056 GJ, 8671 GJ are destroyed, see Figure 3).

Secondly, the renewable exergy efficiency ($\epsilon_{Renewable}$) is analyzed. This represents the percentage of accumulated renewable irreversibilities ($I_{Accumulated-REN}$) relative to the total accumulated irreversibilities ($I_{Accumulated}$). Therefore, the indicator $\epsilon_{Renewable}$ shows the percentage of renewable irreversibilities destroyed relative to the total irreversibilities. In other words, it indicates the renewability of the process. In the 2020 scenario, $\epsilon_{Renewable}$ is 12.9%, meaning that only 12.9% of the lost irreversibilities come from renewable sources. In contrast, in the 2050 scenario, $\epsilon_{Renewable}$ increases to 79.4%. This significant difference is expected, as the deployment of renewable technologies is much more substantial in the 2050 scenario.

After analyzing the circular economy results, it is important to contextualize their implications. The recycling processes studied in this paper are highly efficient in terms of mass recovery, achieving 95% copper recovery and between 98% and 99% recovery for silver, gold, and palladium. However, when all the resources required for this recovery (fuels, electricity, and chemicals) are considered from an exergy perspective, the efficiency drops to 78.9-86.4% ($\epsilon_{Recycling}$). Moreover, when the analysis is extended to include the product manufacturing phases, the exergy efficiency decreases even further to 27.3-49.6% (ϵ_{CE}). This leads to the conclusion that delaying PCB recycling is the best strategy for saving exergy. Each recycling process destroys between 72.7% and 50.4% of the exergy, depending on the scenario. The second law of thermodynamics states that achieving 100% circularity is impossible, but these figures highlight how far current technology is from achieving high circularity, despite

the high material recovery rates. Given the inevitability of irreversibilities, understanding their origin (renewable or non-renewable) is crucial for the sustainability of the circular economy. If the irreversibilities come from renewable sources, they can be replenished by nature in a short period of time, meaning they can be considered "free." On the other hand, non-renewable irreversibilities represent natural resources that are lost forever and therefore unavailable to future generations. In the 2020 scenario, not only is 72.7% of the exergy of the resources destroyed, but 87.1% of these resources are non-renewable, meaning they are lost permanently. In contrast, the 2050 scenario is much more optimistic, as the destruction of exergy decreases to 50.4% and only 20.6% of the resources come from non-renewable sources. However, achieving this level of renewability requires a significant deployment of infrastructure to capture renewable exergy.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- The exergy cost, broken down into exergy and irreversibility, allows for the unification of the resource analysis under the same terms, regardless of whether they refer to energy resources or material resources. On the other hand, it helps identify the processes where more exergy is destroyed. In this way, the most inefficient processes from an exergy perspective can be detected, and solutions can be sought to improve their efficiency.
- The exergy cost can not only be broken down into exergy and irreversibility but also into non-renewable and renewable categories. This breakdown allows for the measurement of the sustainability of processes. Renewable exergy can be replenished by nature in the short term. Thus, although irreversibilities are inevitable, if they can be converted into renewable ones, the sustainability of the process is ensured.
- This dual breakdown of exergy cost (exergy-irreversibility and non-renewable-renewable) allows for the calculation of the circularity and renewability of the economy. Circularity is defined through the exergy efficiency of the circular economy (ϵ_{CE}), which represents the amount of exergy saved in an economic cycle relative to the maximum exergy cost. Renewability is defined through the renewable exergy efficiency ($\epsilon_{Renewable}$), which indicates the percentage of renewable irreversibilities lost relative to the total irreversibilities lost.
- Sankey diagrams are a very useful tool for visualizing the circularity and renewability of the economy. These diagrams can visually capture the origin of exergy, from nature to its use in production processes, showing the processes in which irreversibilities are generated and the composition of the exergy cost, divided into non-renewable and renewable categories.
- This study uses the case of metal recycling from a PCB, showing two scenarios: 2020, representing conventional technologies, and 2050, representing renewable technologies. Although almost all metals are recovered in mass terms (95-99% depending on the metal), ϵ_{CE} ranges between 27.3% and 49.6% for 2020 and 2050, respectively. On the other hand, $\epsilon_{Renewable}$ ranges between 12.9% and 79.4%, respectively. The best results for the 2050 scenario are due to the introduction of renewable technologies, which present fewer irreversibilities and capture more renewable exergy.
- The circular economy can never be 100% circular or 100% renewable, as dictated by the Second Law of Thermodynamics. Therefore, the indicators of circularity and renewability can measure how far society is from this ideal. In this way, the economy could focus its goals on maximizing these indicators through two main strategies: 1) reducing irreversibilities; and 2) developing renewable technologies that capture exergy from nature, thus renewing irreversibilities. These two strategies are key to ensuring the sustainability of production processes in the long term.

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